

Challenge test studies in the framework of Listeriapredict project: evaluation of growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in dynamic conditions

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Abstract

Abstract: A food-associated strain of *Listeria monocytogenes* was grown in broth under different temperature conditions, comparing isothermal (constant temperature) and non-isothermal (variable temperature) conditions that reflects real-world food storage scenarios. Isothermal conditions used temperatures of 4, 8, and 12 degrees C. Non-isothermal conditions used periods of growth at 4 degrees followed by a shift to 12 degrees, and vice versa. The non-isothermal data was used to estimate a secondary model and interpolate a growth rate for 8 degrees, which was similar to the isothermal result. Observations revealed that the *Listeria* growth rate was slightly higher under non-isothermal conditions than predicted from the isothermal-derived secondary model. This suggests the possibility of a 'hysteresis' effect: a phenomenon in which the output (growth rate) is not only dependent on the current input (temperature), but also its past (previous temperature). This research contributes a novel data set, with full sets of data for both isothermal and non-isothermal growth, comparisons of predictions from both sets to the other, and introduces a novel mechanism in predictive microbiological modelling. By incorporating real-world temperature dynamics, these findings add complexity to our understanding of bacterial growth and could enhance the accuracy of shelf-life predictions in food safety management.

Keywords: *Listeria*; isothermal; non-isothermal; dynamic; food safety; predictive microbiology.